

Section 1: Applicants

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Name of the main applicant	Prof. Dr. Tine De Moor
Affiliation – institution	Erasmus University Rotterdam
Affiliation – department	Rotterdam School of Management - Department of Business Society Management
Position	Full Professor
End date of contract	
Guarantee needed & added yes/no/n.a.	
E-mail address	
ORCID ID	

Name of the co-applicant	Margaret Gold
Affiliation – institution	Leiden University
Affiliation – department	Citizen Science Lab, Centre for Science and Technology Studies (CWTS)
Position	Senior Researcher & Coordinator
End date of contract	
Guarantee added yes/no/n.a.	
E-mail address	
ORCID ID	

Name of the co-applicant	Jeroen Melein
Affiliation – institution	Erasmus University Rotterdam
Affiliation – department	Rotterdam School of Management – RSM Digitalisation and Information Service
Position	Director
End date of contract	
Guarantee added yes/no/n.a.	
E-mail address	
ORCID ID	

Name of the co-applicant	Dr. Lukas Held
Affiliation – institution	Erasmus University Rotterdam
Affiliation – department	Rotterdam School of Management - Department of Business Society Management
Position	Scientific Project Coordinator CollectieveKracht
End date of contract	
Guarantee added yes/no/n.a.	
E-mail address	
ORCID ID	

Name of the cooperation partner (person)	Ymke van den Berg
E-mail address	
Organisation	SURF

Section 2: Summary

Proposed project title	Collaborative Research Open Workspace for Networked data (CROWN)
Project duration (in months)	48 months

English public summary
<p>CROWN – an extension of the knowledge exchange platform CollectieveKracht.eu – centralizes existing and emerging datasets on Citizen Collectives. Through CROWN scientists and citizens co-create datasets while reaping benefits in the form of scientific and practical evidence-based insights. CROWN involves citizens in the scientific process, leading to a different citizen-scientist relationship through firsthand experience and tangible outputs. It provides sector-umbrella organizations and policy makers with much needed insights to track the development of this emerging organizational form. CROWN removes barriers to Citizen Science and embraces FAIR and Open Science principles to provide an open-source blueprint to Citizen Science projects in other fields.</p> <p>Word count EN-SUM (max 100): 100</p>

Dutch public summary
<p>CROWN – een uitbreiding van het kennisuitwisselingsplatform CollectieveKracht.eu – centraliseert bestaande en nieuwe datasets over Burgercollectieven. Via CROWN co-creëren wetenschappers en burgers datasets en profiteren zij van wetenschappelijke en praktische inzichten. CROWN betreft burgers actief bij het wetenschappelijk proces, wat leidt tot een vernieuwde relatie tussen burger en wetenschapper door directe ervaring en tastbare resultaten. Het biedt koepelorganisaties en beleidsmakers waardevolle inzichten in de ontwikkeling van deze opkomende organisatievorm. CROWN verlaagt drempels voor Citizen Science en omarmt FAIR- en Open Science-principes, waarmee het een open-source blauwdruk biedt voor Citizen Science-projecten in andere domeinen.</p> <p>Word count NL-SUM (max 100): 91</p>

Section 3: Alignment with the scope of the call

3.1 Vision for the project and alignment with the aim of this call

[CollectieveKracht.eu](https://collectievekracht.eu) is a knowledge exchange platform for stakeholders in the citizen collective ecosystem, supported by [62 researchers](#) from various disciplines, more than [250 citizen collectives \(CCs\)](#) and representatives from all relevant stakeholders. Based on its [extreme citizen science \(CS\)](#)-approach, Collectievekracht empowers Dutch CCs with evidence-based knowledge, by co-developing dual-purpose tools that generate scientifically rigorous research data, while delivering tangible, customized insights for CCs. Growing demand among CCs for tailor-made knowledge, combined with the need to coordinate the increasing requests by scientists to study this phenomenon, calls for a more scalable and high-performing software solution to expand the CollectieveKracht approach.

The [Collaborative Research Open Workspace for Networked data \(CROWN\)](#) project develops such an infrastructure. CROWN integrates data from existing and future dual-purpose tools to create richer datasets on CCs, reducing redundant data collection, and enabling reuse of data. CROWN gives CCs ownership over their data and the initiative to participate in research through useful dual-purpose tools that address their organizational challenges and provides accessible, customized outputs.

CROWN aligns with the call by removing barriers to scalable CS and fosters a new science-citizen relationship. Based on FAIR-principles, open-source values, and SURF infrastructure, it serves as a blueprint for CS-projects in other domains.

Word count SEC31 (max. 200): 200

3.2 User communities, challenges and needs

CCs -as an emerging type of economic and societal organization- face challenges which established types of organizations like corporations or government bodies do not face (De Moor et al., 2025). Hence, CCs have a higher need for evidence-based knowledge to develop into resilient organizations. Currently, this knowledge is scarce, scattered, too generic and insufficiently applicable. Because of their fragility and lack of resources, CCs struggle to gather the needed knowledge independently. They frequently approach CollectieveKracht looking for insights on issues ranging from governance structures to member motivation. The existing CollectieveKracht-network and the broader CC-ecosystem need more accessible, evidence-based knowledge to support their efforts in creating conditions that enable CCs to reach their full potential in societal transitions. As the [Impact Explorer-project](#) made clear: CC-umbrella organizations also lack capacity and expertise to systematically gather data to meet these needs, leading to fragmented and incomplete overviews of the CC-landscape.

The model which CollectieveKracht currently uses to share evidence-based knowledge is, as the movement grows, not a scalable model. CROWN -as an extension of CollectieveKracht's CS-approach- solves these issues: CROWN connects research projects to their findability, enables CCs to participate in research based on their needs and incentivizes uses of the dual-purpose tools, providing tailor-made insights.

This fundamental change in relationships between scientists and CCs is necessary as growing scientific interest in CCs is met with reluctance from CCs to participate in research, due to time constraints and limited capacity ([Volkskrant, 2023](#)). Because available data are fragmented, inconsistent, and of insufficient quality, researchers need better access and more reliable datasets to advance our understanding of this emerging organizational form. CROWN addresses this gap by offering scientists a comprehensive overview of existing datasets and ongoing data collection related to CCs. By preventing duplication and fostering coordination, CROWN facilitates more efficient allocation of research resources.

Word count SEC32 (max. 300): 300

3.3 Alignment of project with OS principles

We align CROWN with the strategic goals of NPOS2030, both conceptually and technically, to advance Open Science.

Towards Societal Engagement and Participation

CROWN scales CollectieveKracht's citizen involvement model across the scientific process. By fostering dialogue between citizens and scientists, it enhances data quality and scientific output while increasing understanding of science through firsthand experience. CCs can propose research questions, initiate studies, access tailored outputs, and control how their data is used.

CROWN's participatory governance model makes CCs active stakeholders in identity, consent, and access management. This ensures data sovereignty and positions CCs as co-owners in decision-making. Access is role-based and transparent, with results shared via citizen-facing dashboards.

Towards Inclusive and Transparent Scientific Processes

CROWN promotes transparency by engaging CCs early in research and offering tangible outputs in return. Researchers who contribute to reciprocal knowledge-sharing gain access to datasets and are encouraged to collaborate in the Collaborative Workspace. This supports reproducibility, data reuse, and verification. Sanitized sample datasets will be publicly available to foster collaboration and openness.

Towards FAIR and Open Research Outputs

CROWN enhances dataset findability, accessibility, and interoperability by integrating and organizing data from various disciplines. Clear access guidelines for data reuse ensure efficient usage of resources and reduce the burden on CCs and support reproducibility. By integrating data from various disciplines CROWN improves interoperability.

The infrastructure will use open protocols (e.g. SAML, OIDC) and community-based standards to ensure interoperability and integration with the European Open Science Cloud (EOSC) ecosystem. All core components will be developed or released under open-source licenses, whenever possible, enabling reuse, transparency, and long-term sustainability.

CROWN's design is modular and re-usable. Other research groups aiming to enhance citizen engagement and data sovereignty can adopt or adapt the technical and governance models developed here. This extends the impact of the project well beyond its initial domain.

Word count SEC33 (max. 300): 300

3.4 Access policy

User access to the CROWN-infrastructure is free of charge and organised via SURF Research Access Management (SRAM), which provides secure and federated access for both institutional researchers and non-institutional data subjects. Researchers authenticate through their institutional accounts and access datasets via SURF Research Cloud environments. Data subjects, including members of CCs authenticate using eduID. In line with CollectieveKracht-policy on ownership and co-creation, CCs manage group membership and delegate access permissions using SRAM's collaboration functionality (WP6).

Access to sensitive data environments is restricted to data stewards, who configure collaborations and evaluate access requests of researchers together with data owners, taking into account privacy, security, and research intent as well as previous contributions to the reciprocal process of knowledge sharing at CollectieveKracht.

Data subjects gain access to tools and research outputs via collective-level permissions. Where necessary, data or insights may be exchanged with existing and future platforms, manually or through future integration.

Word count SEC34 (max. 150): 150

3.5 (Inter)national ecosystem

Whereas CollectieveKracht represents the CC-ecosystem, CROWN builds on and strengthens the Dutch and European Open Science ecosystem, aligning with the EOSC Multi-Annual Roadmap and the National Roadmap for Large-Scale Research Infrastructures. It is designed to be interoperable, standards-based, and reusable across domains.

SURF is a confirmed collaborator, providing identity and access management (via SRAM and eduID) and workspace environments (via SURF Research Cloud). This ensures both researchers and CCs can securely interact with the infrastructure. The proposed infrastructure enhances these capabilities by introducing structured access control, consent management, and citizen-led group governance.

Collaboration with DANS is under development, particularly for sustainable data archiving and metadata standardization. A potential to link with ODISSEI will be further explored, with a focus on aligning with national social science datasets and data access governance. Through the consortium members' strong links to the Dutch and European Open and Citizen networks – including the Citizen Science NL network and with proven expertise as shown in a recent OECD publication on CS, CROWN will be at the forefront of CS. The connection with these networks will allow us to disseminate the proposed infrastructure widely and make it available to interested parties beyond the immediate scope of this project.

Word count SEC35 (max. 200): 200

Section 4: Feasibility

4.1 Project plan

CROWN is organized into six work packages (WPs) (Figure 1), each addressing a key functional or infrastructural layer. The work packages follow a modular structure, allowing for parallel development, coordinated in WP1 (Figure 2).

WP1: Project Management & CollectieveKracht-Integration

This WP ensures coordination and quality assurance, integrating the CollectieveKracht co-creation approach into CROWN. We will establish a continuous feedback cycle through stakeholder workshops, structurally involving CCs and civil society partners in decision-making and design. This ensures user groups co-develop consent flows and data controls and community protocols that support data sovereignty and social license. This approach is based on the established and tested [CollectieveKracht extreme CS approach](#).

The WP also covers transferring CollectieveKracht resources to CROWN and organizing outreach, including a national CS conference to disseminate CROWN as a blueprint for other CS projects.

WP2: Data Vault & Refinery Lock

This WP focuses on secure data storage and controlled access. Using SURF Research Cloud, the Data Vault offers encrypted, access-controlled storage for raw and processed data. The Refinery Lock, a custom-built software layer, governs preprocessing and approval before data release. Approved datasets are pushed to the Vault via a REST API (WP4). Testing and audit trail documentation, as well as embargo, review, and anonymization policies are designed by experienced IT experts at the Rotterdam School of Management Digitalisation & Information Services department (RDIS). Conditions for data reuse will be co-created with CCs and researchers (WP1).

WP3: Collaborative Workspace

The Collaborative Workspace (CW) offers a secure, role-based environment for researchers to analyse data and collaborate. It includes configurable permissions, co-authoring of research protocols, dataset tagging, discussion threads, changelogs, and shared notebooks—fostering transparency and collaboration across projects

WP4: API Layer and Interoperability

WP4 connects CROWN to external tools and ensures compliance with FAIR principles through standardized, machine-readable interfaces. Software Engineers and Testers will implement three key APIs:

1. **Vault API** – for pushing (meta)data to the Vault and retrieving metadata in formats like DCAT and schema.org.
2. **CW API** – to share individualized research reports from the CW to the Insights platform.
3. **Library Sample API** – for accessing sanitized dataset samples and handling access requests.

Interoperability with DANS, ODISEI, and SURF tooling will be explored, enabling citizen-generated data to flow into broader research infrastructures under clear reuse terms.

WP5: Views & Insights (Communication Layer)

This WP transforms research outputs into meaningful insights. The Insights platform allows CCs to view customized outputs from the research they have engaged in and initiate participation in research by using dual-purpose tools based on their needs. The CW API (WP4) connects reports to Insights, with output formats determined during early implementation for future scalability.

A synthesised, anonymised dataset sample list—prepared by data stewards — will be made publicly available through the Library Sample API (WP4) in Views. This supports FAIR data reuse and allows interested researchers to request access to datasets. A clear communication and documentation strategy is a key aspect of CROWN and makes it accessible to diverse societal partners, especially CCs, with varying levels of digital literacy.

WP6: Access Management

WP6 manages secure, ethical access to CROWN's services through federated identity and fine-grained, context-

aware permissions. Integration with SURF’s SRAM and eduID enables role- and purpose-based access. A consent interface links to both datasets and user actions, while robust logging and audit trails ensure accountability across the platform.

Figure 1: CROWN project-structure

Figure 2: CROWN-timeline

Word count SEC 41 (max. 750): 744

4.2 Team composition

Name, surname	Affiliation	Expertise	Role/contributions
Prof. dr. Tine De Moor	EUR	Open and Citizen Science, Citizen Collectives	As an acclaimed researcher in open and citizen science she will ensure CROWN is built according to CS-principles with the needs of both researchers and CCs in mind. Her vast experience as lead applicant will help manage CROWN successfully (WP1).
Margaret Gold	University of Leiden	Open and Citizen Science, Open Science Platforms	With extensive CS and IT-project experience, she helps define user requirements in stakeholder workshops (WP1), develops the CC onboarding flow (WP6), and leverages her CS-NL network to support CROWN's dissemination (WP1)
Jeroen Melein	EUR	Information Management	As information manager, he ensures CROWN's alignment with FAIR principles, shapes identity and access management and governance, and links user needs to sustainable design (WP2-6)
Dr. Lukas Held	EUR	Project Management, Stakeholder engagement, Citizen Collectives	As CollectieveKracht's scientific coordinator, he organizes the participation of CCs and stakeholders in the development process and oversees the transfer of resources from CollectieveKracht to CROWN (WP1, 5).
NN	EUR	Embedded Data Steward	Will establish data processing and access protocols and data taxonomies, as well as integrate existing CollectieveKracht data resources into CROWN (WP2).
NN	EUR	Communication Officer	Will develop communication material and documentation (WP5) to make CROWN accessible and user-friendly for diverse stakeholder groups.
NN	EUR	IT Implementation Manager	Plays a key role in translating user requirements from WP1 into infrastructure solutions (WP2, 3, 4, 6) and in creating accessible documentation for all stakeholders (WP5).
Simon Gerritsen	EUR	Software Management	Coordinate the Software Engineers and Tester, (WP 2 - 6).
Ir. Adriaan Bleys	EUR	Software Testing	Will be responsible for providing quality assurance of the produced features. (WP 2 - 6).
Govert Buijs	EUR	Software Engineering	Will be responsible for writing code following quality guidelines (WP 2 - 6).
Erik Kemperman	EUR	Software Engineering	Will be responsible for writing code following quality guidelines (WP 2 - 6).
Ymke van den Berg	SURF	Data Infrastructure	Advisor and point of contact at SURF to ensure the project's alignment with SURF and optimal use of SURF's products. (WP 2, 3, 6).

Word count SEC42 (max. 350): 350

4.3 Risk management

Risk	Likelihood and impact	Risk mitigation strategy
Low adoption by researchers or collectives	Likelihood: medium Impact: high	Engage pilot users from both groups at an early stage during development; co-create documentation and onboarding flows; provide lightweight training and insight-sharing mechanisms to build trust and visibility.
Complexity of SRAM integration for collectives	Likelihood: medium Impact: medium	Collaborate closely with SURF (confirmed partner) to adapt SRAM collaboration models for non-institutional users; develop layered support material and test configurations in sandbox environments.
Metadata model or taxonomy not interoperable or reusable	Likelihood: medium Impact: medium	Align early with national and EOSC metadata standards (e.g. via DANS); validate models in WP1 with multiple use cases and feedback from FAIR experts.
Sustainability responsibilities not secured after grant	Likelihood: Low Impact: high	Formalize RDIS and CollectieveKracht responsibilities during the project; explore scaling options with EUR partners (Library, Research Support) or through consortium models like Yoda.
Legal or ethical challenges related to data subject access and consent	Likelihood: medium Impact: high	Include consent management and group governance in the design; consult legal experts during WP1; align with GDPR and practices in existing infrastructures (e.g. ODISSEI, SRAM).

The CROWN-project builds a modular, FAIR-aligned infrastructure for citizen-led research, integrating SURF services and open science tools. Key risks span engagement, interoperability, governance, and compliance, with mitigation embedded through collaboration, agile development, and institutional support for long-term resilience. Given the availability of a functional and well-recognized platform, Collectievekracht, and well-developed research support infrastructure (RDIS), problems can be identified at an early stage.

Word count SEC43 (max. 250): 250

4.4 Budget

Total budget requested: € 1.496.453,00

4.5 Budget justification

Tine De Moor has vast experience as a Principal Investigator of large research projects, and years of experience with the roll-out of CS research projects like CollectieveKracht. CROWN will profit from this experience in setting up a sound project structure and her insights into effective researcher-CC interaction. Margaret Gold complements these competencies with her strong track-record of delivering CS IT projects. With the project coordinator of CollectieveKracht (at 0.25 FTE) CROWN gets an experienced daily project manager who ensures that CROWN makes optimal use of the existing CollectieveKracht-network and its extensive resources. All three consortium members have organized numerous stakeholder dialogue sessions and will oversee the stakeholder workshops as part of the feedback loop.

Jeroen Melein spearheads the development team with more than 2 decades of experience in delivering complex IT infrastructure projects combined with stakeholder involvement. Simon Gerritsen will supervise the competent team of in-house developers who all have years of experience working with various SURF products. This team is completed by a data steward who defines data processing steps and taxonomies, in addition to the IT Implementation Manager who serves as a bridge between the development team and the user requirements collected in WP1. Material costs are limited to webhosting and SURF Infrastructure support.

Dissemination and stakeholder outreach play an integral role in CROWN. This is reflected in the budget: a communications officer will produce communications material and will, in collaboration with the IT Implementation Manager, ensure that the technical documentation is presented in a language and format that is appropriate for the various stakeholder groups. These efforts are supported by third parties in lay-outing the documentation and communicating materials and the user web interface. Budget is reserved for disseminating CROWN into the CS community by means of organizing one scientific conference and participating in two others.

Word count SEC45 (max. 300): 299

4.6 Impact plan

CROWN's primary impact lies in dramatically improving the knowledge base about CCs in the Netherlands. This will impact not only scientists' ability to provide more and better analysis of this emerging type of organization but will also allow practitioners from umbrella organizations to monitor the developments in their respective sector more accurately. The additional insights provide policy makers with a better understanding of the role CCs can play in society.

Crucially, CROWN will impact CCs directly by making customized and evidence-based insights available to CCs on a larger scale. This drastically improves the basis for decision-making within CCs and helps accelerate their development. By giving CCs more ownership in the research process, facilitating tangible outcomes, and empowering CCs to initiate research as they see fit, CROWN impacts the citizen-scientist relationship fundamentally and increases trust into science through first-hand experience.

Projects in other domains that aim to involve citizens in similar fashion greatly profit from the blueprint CROWN provides. CROWN removes several hurdles to data collection in CS and its focus on strengthening the data layer make it a reusable model across disciplines. The applicant is already engaged in talks with fledging initiatives in medical science and social media research.

Word count SEC46 (max. 200): 199

Section 5: Sustainability and software management

Section 5.1: Sustainability plan

The outcomes of this project include a modular, FAIR-aligned data infrastructure (data vault, metadata-model, APIs), access governance integrated with SURF SRAM and eduID, lightweight dashboards for research feedback, open documentation, and reusable open-source components. These components together support participatory and reciprocal research between academic institutions and CCs.

After the grant period, a clear role distribution amongst the project partners is in place to safeguard the long-term sustainability of the infrastructure: by relying on SURF services as the backbone of CROWN, maintenance of the core components is ensured. The RSM Digitalisation & Information Services department (RDIS) will strive to maintain the customized technical components of the platform, including the data vault, access control integrations, and APIs. CollectieveKracht will focus on user support, documentation, community engagement, and operational workflows.

The research group in which CollectieveKracht is embedded in has continuously shown substantial success in securing both scientific and impact funding to operate the platform. However, due to a lack of specific OS/digital infrastructure calls, building a new CS-infrastructure through this route has so far proven unattainable. CROWN will provide the basis for multiple future funding applications that will contribute to maintaining the infrastructure.

The infrastructure is intentionally designed to be reusable by research groups beyond the initial CC-context. The lead applicant is already in talks with CS-projects in other domains, for example in the medical field. Furthermore, with the European roll-out of CollectieveKracht, currently in preparation for Belgium and France, the CROWN-results will be used across Europe. This increases the return on investment and amplifies the long-term societal and scientific impact. Reuse will be supported through clear technical documentation, open APIs, and community-led examples. Through our alignment with SURF as a collaboration partner, we will continue to explore ways to integrate CROWN into the national CS infrastructure.

As multiple stakeholder groups, like sector-umbrella organizations and policy makers, have expressed interest in the past into receiving better data on the development of Citizen Collectives in the Netherlands in general and certain sectors specifically, we will further explore these avenues to involve stakeholders in covering the maintenance costs of CROWN in exchange for valuable insights provided by the platform.

Software developed under this project will be released under a CC BY-NC open source license to support transparency, reproducibility, and community reuse.

In summary, the project outcomes are embedded in existing institutional structures, technically modular, and open by design—ensuring continuity, extensibility, and strategic alignment with the broader goals of Open Science and FAIR digital infrastructure.

Word count SEC51 (450): 411

Section 5.2: Software management plan

This Software Management Plan (SMP) follows the guidance provided in the *Practical Guide to Software Management Plans* (Scholtens et al., 2023) and addresses all recommended core components. These include purpose, audience, licensing, documentation, citation, versioning, accessibility, governance, testing, packaging, support, and long-term sustainability. The table below offers a summary mapping of these components to the relevant sections of this plan:

SMP Requirement	Addressed in Section
1. Purpose and intended audience	5.2.1
2. Version control	5.2.2
3. Licensing	5.2.3
4. Citation and persistent identifiers	5.2.4
5. Documentation (user/developer/install)	5.2.5

6. Contribution and governance	5.2.6
7. Testing	5.2.7
8. License compliance	5.2.8
9. Packaging and distribution	5.2.9
10. Support and maintenance	5.2.10–11

1. Please provide a brief description of your software, stating its purpose and intended audience.

The software developed within the CROWN project will consist of modular components supporting collaborative, FAIR-aligned research with CCs. Key elements include a data vault with structured metadata and taxonomy support, a data refinery for pre-processing and validation, and a RESTful API layer for secure, role-based access to datasets. Additional tools will facilitate delegated group access management via SURF SRAM, and lightweight dashboards will allow collectives to view tailored research outputs.

The intended audience includes researchers working with non-institutional data subjects, data stewards responsible for curating and securing datasets, and representatives of CCs who manage group-level access and consent. The software will enable these stakeholders to collaborate transparently and securely, while preserving data sovereignty for participants.

2. How will you manage versioning of your software?

Versioning will follow semantic versioning (SemVer) principles, using a major.minor.patch structure (e.g. 1.2.0) to indicate the nature and scope of changes. All code will be hosted on a public repository, with each release clearly tagged and documented.

Changelogs will accompany each release, and versioned branches will distinguish between stable production-ready code and ongoing development. Dependencies will be version-pinned to ensure reproducibility. This setup enables contributors and downstream users to track changes over time and maintain compatibility with evolving infrastructure components.

3. How will you make your software publicly available? What licence will your software have?

All software developed in the CROWN project will be made available through a publicly accessible repository. The repository will include source code, changelogs, technical documentation, and contribution guidelines to support reuse and transparency. Stable releases will be archived with persistent identifiers (e.g. via Zenodo) to enable proper citation and long-term accessibility.

All software components developed in the CROWN project will be released under an OSI-approved open-source license such as the MIT or Apache 2.0 license, to ensure maximum reusability, compatibility, and community uptake. This replaces the previous CC BY-NC license plan for source code, which is not recommended for software.

Non-code deliverables such as documentation, infographics, and outreach materials will be licensed under Creative Commons (e.g. CC BY-NC), provided they do not form part of the executable software stack.

4. How will users of your software be able to cite your software?

We will ensure that all CROWN software components are citable by registering them with persistent identifiers. Stable releases will be archived via Zenodo, which automatically assigns a DOI and supports integration with public repositories. Metadata will include authorship, versioning, institutional affiliation, and funding information.

Citation records will also be deposited in PURE, the Erasmus University Rotterdam research information system, to ensure discoverability and attribution through institutional channels. The recommended citation format will be provided in the README file of each repository and on the Zenodo landing page.

This approach aligns with EUR’s research data management and citation policy and supports reproducibility, proper attribution, and long-term access.

5. How will your software be documented? Please describe your plans for: user documentation, documentation for future developers and for installation requirements. Please provide links to documentation if already available.

Documentation for CROWN will follow a layered approach, targeting different user groups: researchers, data stewards, developers, and collective delegates. We will adopt a best-practice model inspired by infrastructures such

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as SURF SRAM, using a centralized Wiki environment (e.g. Confluence) as the main access point for all documentation:

- User documentation will include step-by-step guides for accessing and interacting with the data vault, using the API layer, managing collaborations in SRAM, and viewing insights through dashboards. It will be written in accessible language and tested with both researchers and representatives from CCs.
- Developer documentation will cover system architecture, API specifications, authentication/authorization models, and extension points. It will be version-controlled and linked directly from the repository.
- Installation requirements and deployment instructions (e.g. for local testing or containerized deployment) will be maintained alongside the codebase, using standard formats like README.md and docker-compose.yml.

Documentation will be openly accessible and maintained by CollectieveKracht and RDIS beyond the project's duration. Links will be added once the repository and Wiki are publicly available.

6. How will contribution guidelines and governance structure of your software be documented?

Contribution guidelines will be published in the main repository, following established community standards. A CONTRIBUTING.md file will outline the process for submitting issues, proposing features, contributing code, and engaging in discussions. This will include code style requirements, testing protocols, and review procedures. The repository will also include a CODE_OF_CONDUCT.md to ensure respectful and inclusive collaboration.

The governance structure of the software will be lightweight but transparent. [CollectieveKracht's management team](#) will coordinate user engagement and feedback, while RDIS will oversee technical quality and roadmap planning. Decisions on major changes or releases will be made collaboratively between these two partners and in alignment with the other stakeholders, documented through release notes and update logs., documented through release notes and update logs.

The governance model, including roles and responsibilities, decision-making processes, and criteria for accepting contributions, will be included in the project Wiki. This ensures both clarity for external contributors and continuity over time.

7. How will your software be tested?

Software developed within the CROWN project will be tested using a combination of automated and manual methods. The RDIS-development team includes a dedicated software tester who will be responsible for designing and executing the test strategy.

Testing will include:

- ✓ Unit tests for individual components,
- ✓ Integration tests to ensure reliable interactions across APIs and systems (e.g. SRAM, data vault, dashboards),
- ✓ User acceptance testing (UAT) with both researchers and collective representatives to validate usability and functional requirements.

Test cases, coverage, and results will be documented and version-controlled within the repository. Each release will be validated against these criteria before deployment.

8. How will you check that it respects the licences of libraries and dependencies it uses?

All software components developed in the CROWN project will follow a documented dependency management process. The RDIS development team uses standard tools (e.g., pip-licenses) to identify and track third-party library usage and ensure compliance with their licenses.

Dependencies will be reviewed during development and prior to each release. Only libraries with permissive or compatible open-source licenses (e.g. MIT, Apache 2.0, BSD) will be approved for integration. Any exceptions or special licensing conditions will be documented in the repository and in the software's metadata.

The software tester at RDIS will include license compliance as part of the release checklist, ensuring that all software respects the terms of use for included libraries and frameworks.

9. How will your software be packaged and distributed?

The CROWN software will be distributed through public repositories hosted by the Erasmus University Rotterdam (EUR) organization. Releases will be versioned and archived with persistent identifiers, ensuring long-term accessibility and citability.

Each component will be packaged based on its function:

- ✓ Web services and APIs will be distributed as Docker containers with accompanying docker-compose.yml files and environment templates.
- ✓ Libraries or utilities (e.g. for metadata handling) will be packaged as separate modules and published via Releases.
- ✓ Documentation and installation instructions will be included in each package and centrally maintained in the project Wiki.

Dependencies will be clearly listed and pinned to ensure reproducibility.

To support external adoption and reproducibility, we plan to host Docker images of major components (e.g. APIs, dashboards) on a public container registry (e.g. GitHub Container Registry or DockerHub), alongside the code repositories. If feasible, we will also deploy a sandbox environment or public demo instance to facilitate exploration and onboarding by third-party users.

10. What level of support will be provided for users of the software and how will this support be organised?

User support for the CROWN software will be coordinated by CollectieveKracht in partnership with RSM's Digitalisation & Information Services (RDIS). Support is primarily focused on internal users—researchers, data stewards, and CCs—who interact with the infrastructure as part of CROWN's core use cases.

However, a public Wiki-based knowledge base (e.g. Confluence) will provide comprehensive self-service support, including installation instructions, user and admin guides, API documentation, and FAQs. The GitHub repository will contain issue tracking for technical feedback and bug reporting.

CollectieveKracht will provide first-line operational support during onboarding and piloting phases. RDIS will manage second-line technical maintenance for the deployed infrastructure, focusing on institutional continuity. For external re-users of the software, no direct support is provided beyond publicly available documentation and the issue tracker. Reuse is encouraged but self-directed.

11. How do you plan to ensure long term maintenance of your software?

Long-term maintenance of the CROWN software will be secured through institutional embedding and a modular governance model. Initially, the technical infrastructure will be maintained by RSM's Digitalisation & Information Services (RDIS), while CollectieveKracht will oversee operational support, documentation, and community engagement. As the backbone of CROWN is formed by SURF products maintenance of these major building blocks is ensured.

As adoption grows—within EUR or across other institutions—the project team will explore transitioning the infrastructure to a university-wide or inter-institutional support structure, drawing inspiration from the Yoda Consortium model. In this model, multiple Dutch universities, including EUR, collaborate to ensure sustainable development, governance, and shared ownership of the Yoda research data platform. A similar consortium-based approach for CROWN would allow participating institutions to pool resources, coordinate support, and extend CROWN's applicability across domains.

Potential future stewardship could involve the Erasmus University Library, Erasmus Research Support, or a national-level collaborative structure, potentially in partnership with SURF or DANS. In the meantime, the software will remain open source (CC BY-NC) and versioned, ensuring it remains reusable and adaptable, even outside a formal support structure. This hybrid strategy ensures both short-term continuity and long-term scalability, with governance models aligned to national best practices.

Section 6: References

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Section 7: Declaration

By submitting this form, I declare that:

- I and all the individuals involved in this proposal satisfy the nationally and internationally accepted standards for scientific conduct as stated in the Netherlands [Code of Conduct for Research Integrity](#) (The Universities of the Netherlands).
- The research organisation has been informed of this grant application and the research organisation accepts the grant conditions of this programme.
- I have completed this application form truthfully.
- I have submitted a pre-proposal for this Call for proposals in ISAAC.